

Ethics-by-design: A values framework for open web search

Christine Plote^a, Renée Ridgway^b and Daniela Zetti^c

^a *Open Search Foundation, Germany*

^b *Aarhus University, Denmark*

^c *ETH Zurich, Switzerland*

1. From gatekeepers to open infrastructure

Web search's societal significance has grown steadily, establishing it as 'fundamental information infrastructure' 'for knowing and becoming informed' (Haider & Sundin, 2019), for accessing knowledge, education and public discourse. However, search engine development, operation and governance is concentrated among few corporations, with Google holding ~90%² of the market through billions of users' 'ubiquitous googling' (Ridgway 2021, 2023). These corporations can shape what individuals find online, which perspectives are visible and how decisions are made (see, e.g., Introna & Nissenbaum, 2000a; Haider & Sundin, 2019; Graham, 2023).

Driven by commercial interests, often opposing democratic values and the roots of the web as an open platform, their business models rely on proprietary indices and opaque algorithms, while blocking competition (Harvard Law Review, 2024). Structural biases and discrimination persist and intensified with Google's growing dominance (Noble, 2018; Mager et al., 2023), furthering inequalities and social disadvantages.

Systematic user and behavioural data collection for advertising is central to the business. Google has developed a multifaceted 'service/data profile/advertising complex' (Lovink & Tkacz, 2015), exploiting user data and driving 'data colonialism' (Couldry & Mejias 2019). This 'logic of accumulation' creates power imbalances (Zuboff 2015; 2019), undermining transparency, pluralism and democratic control – and endangering fundamental rights like privacy and freedom of information. Already in 2000, Introna & Nissenbaum (2000b) argued search engines are too important 'to be shaped by the marketplace alone' and 'must work in the greater public interest'. Zuboff (2019) asserts that 'at stake here is the human expectation of sovereignty over one's own life and authorship of one's own experience'.

To address this disparity, the EU has funded the Horizon Europe project OpenWebSearch.EU (OWS.EU)³ since September 2022. The project designs and prototypes an Open Web Index (OWI)⁴, based on 'European values and jurisdiction'. Inspired by Lewandowski's (2014; 2019) 'Independent Index of the Web' concept and related principles (Granitzer et al., 2023), it creates not another search engine, but an open, federated web index infrastructure for multiple search services and other applications. Unlike commercial search engines controlling both index and search interface, the OWI separates web search infrastructure from the search engine layer. By establishing the index as a public-good, 'new

SEASON 2025, September 24–25, 2025, Hamburg, Germany

EMAIL: cp@opensearchfoundation.org (A. 1), rridgway@cc.au.dk (A. 2), zettid@ethz.ch (A. 3)

ORCID: 0000-0002-1483-9996 (A. 2), 0000-0003-1188-5054 (A. 3)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17156319>

© 2025 Copyright for this paper by its authors.
Use permitted under Creative Commons License Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

² <https://gs.statcounter.com/search-engine-market-share#monthly-202501-202501-bar>; January 25; retrieved on 13 August

³ <https://openwebsearch.eu>

⁴ <https://openwebindex.eu>; The prototype was launched in June 2025.

open web information intermediary' (Hendriksen et al., 2024), it encourages innovation and competition at the application level, stimulating European sovereignty in navigating and searching the web.

2. Building Ethical Foundations

Web search should serve people, not vice versa. Based on this premise, the Open Search Foundation (OSF)⁵, initiated a collaborative multi-stakeholder process alongside OWI development. Through workshops, experts from academia, civil society and technology – notably OSF's Ethics Working Group⁶ and the OWS.eu project – examined political and socio-technical issues in web search. The aim was developing foundations of an ethical framework for a search landscape that upholds individual rights, enables participation and strengthens personal and collective autonomy. Using 'ethics-by-design' approaches per Nussbaumer et al. (2023), the group explored how the OWI and (search) applications based on it could become, in Feenberg's terms (2021), a 'legitimate object of political struggle', and how the design and use of web search can foster effective collaborations and generate ethical oversight.

The concept of the OWI is, by design, a counterpoint to the big players' commercial, data-hungry search engines due to its open, federated, open-source, and non-commercial nature. However, technology is not neutral, desired outcomes and potential unintended consequences must be considered beforehand.

From outset, it was clear that the OWI should uphold fundamental values like human dignity, democracy and human rights, enshrined in the EU Treaty and in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. However, deciding which specific values to integrate into OWI's standards, code and processes, and how to do so, requires thorough consideration. Rather than adapting existing ethical frameworks for digital technologies, the group opted for an exploratory 'blank page' approach. Focusing on 'What values need to be included in the development, governance, and operation of an open, federated web index as a public good?', they identified core values, stakeholders, risks, and mitigation strategies specific to (open) web search and the OWI (see Figure 1).

⁵ The Open Search Foundation is an independent non-profit organisation and project partner of OWS.eu; <https://opensearchfoundation.org>

⁶ <https://ethicsinsearch.org/en/osf-wg-ethics/>

Ethics-by-Design Process for the Open Web Index

This schematic representation simplifies a not entirely linear process. Topics were addressed iteratively across blocks, with recursive loops for coordination and validation, especially in value definition.

2025 | www.ethicsinsearch.org / opensearchfoundation.org

Figure 1: Development process

The group initially compiled a longlist of 50 values, then narrowed these to 10 core values (figure 2). For each core value, they determined building blocks including definitions, the values’ role in relation to web search, stakeholder impact, and implementation criteria. Since values can mean different things for different people, based on background or experience for example, establishing a shared understanding was an intensive but crucial part of the project.

2025 | www.ethicsinsearch.org / opensearchfoundation.org

Figure 2: Core values and scheme for building blocks

Risk-Value-Mitigation Matrix		Tackled Values										Importance (Severity/Probability)		Impact	Affected Stakeholders	Mitigation Strategies / Measures Technical, Organisational	
Risk/ Violation	Risk description	Transparency	Safety/Security	Openness	Responsibility	Privacy	Justice	Trustworthiness	Accountability	Sustainability / Social Responsibility	Sovereignty / Autonomy	Severity	Probability	Impact	Affected Stakeholders	Mitigation Strategies/Measures: Technical	Mitigation Strategies/Measures: organisational
Misconduct	Users of OWI (e.g. Data products and search applications) do not adhere to the license agreements; use the OWI for malfeasance Improper content not taken down misuse of index for criminal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Extreme	High	people losing trust in OWI	OWI operators/owners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If a data product is public, one could look for content that should be taken down and prevent future downloads in case of violations • Stronger authentication / identification for ethical / legal more problematic usages • Incident Response: Establishing procedures for quickly responding to and mitigating security incidents. • Panic Button 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reporting mechanisms + set of rules + measures to actually do them (structure)/procedure for reporting violations, set up contact points, structure for reporting, internal documentation process) • Ethical self-assessment as a filter • code of ethics for advertising and content curation practices • Stakeholder Management, preventing anonymization of users • set up structure for legal evaluation

Figure 3: Risk-value mitigation matrix

The results, e.g. in form of a *value-risk-mitigation matrix* (figure 3), illustrate stakeholder politics (society, content creators, third-party developers, users) and highlight ethical concerns. They show how results enable oversight and user empowerment – prerequisites for digital sovereignty.

3. Impact and next steps

The ethical principles guide practical implementations within OpenWebSearch.eu, informing OWI procedures, content analysis, and developer guidelines.

Key implementations include the *OWI Ethics Readiness Check*, a voluntary online assessment for OWI users to evaluate their own compliance with the OWI’s ethical and legal criteria. Users receive guidance on measures they can take to better meet the requirements for developing ‘value-compliant’ applications based on the OWI. Another outcome is OWI developers’ mindset shift towards viewing ethical values as integral to the OWI architecture rather than optional extras or barriers.

However, as a living system, the framework requires critical reflection, uptake and discussion. Follow-up steps include governance analyses, a manifesto⁷ and visualisations to stimulate debate about web search ethics and oversight. This ensures that the OWI provides technical alternatives to commercial search engines while embodying a different vision of public-interest web search infrastructure.

4. Acknowledgements

The authors are all members of the Open Search Foundation’s Ethics Working Group⁸. This work draws on the group’s collaborative efforts over the past few years. The views expressed are those of the authors.

The authors would like to thank the Stiftung Mercator⁹ and the CAIS Center of Advanced Internet Studies for facilitating workshops.

The project OpenWebSearch.EU has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101070014.

⁷ At the time of writing, the manifesto had not yet been made public. It will be available at <https://freewebssearch.org/en/manifesto>.

⁸ [https:// ethicsinsearch.org/en/osf-wg-ethics](https://ethicsinsearch.org/en/osf-wg-ethics)

⁹ The Mercator Foundation has funded the Open Search Foundation as part of the #EthicsInSearch project. The project promotes greater ethics and transparency in web search. <https://ethicsinsearch.org>

5. References

Couldry, N. & Mejias, U. (2019). *The Costs of Connection: How Data Is Colonizing Human Life and Appropriating It for Capitalism*. Stanford: Stanford University Press

Feenberg, A. (2017). Critical theory of technology and STS. *Thesis Eleven*, 138(1), 3–12

Graham, R. (2023). The ethical dimensions of Google autocomplete. *Big Data & Society*, 10(1), 20539517231156518. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517231156518>

Granitzer, M., Voigt, S., Fathima, N. A., Golasowski, M., Guetl, C., Hecking, T., Hendriksen, G., Hiemstra, D., Martinovič, J., Mitrović, J., Mlakar, I., Moiras, S., Nussbaumer, A., Öster, P., Potthast, M., Senčar Srdič, M., Sharikadze, M., Slaninová, K., Stein, B., & Wrigley, S. N. (2023). Impact and development of an Open Web Index for open web search. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 75(5), 512–520. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24818>

Haider, J., Sundin O. (2019). *Invisible Search and Online Search Engines – The Ubiquity of Search in Everyday Life*. London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429448546>

Harvard Law Review (2024). United States v. Google, LLC – U.S. District Court for the District of Columbia Imposes Liability on Google for Engaging in Anticompetitive Conduct as a Monopolist. *Harvard Law Review*, 138 Harv. L. Rev. 891. <https://harvardlawreview.org/print/vol-138/united-states-v-google-llc>

Hendriksen, G. *et al.* (2024). The Open Web Index. In: Goharian, N., *et al.* *Advances in Information Retrieval*. ECIR 2024. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 14612. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-56069-9_10

Introna, L. & Nissenbaum, H. (2000a). Shaping The Web: Why The Politics Of Search Engines Matters. *The Information Society*, 16. 169-185. 10.1080/01972240050133634.

Introna, L. & Nissenbaum, H. (2000b). Defining the Web: The Politics of Search Engines. *Computer*. 33. 54 - 62. 10.1109/2.816269.

Lewandowski, D. (2014). Why we need an independent index of the Web. In R. König & M. Rasch (Eds.), *Society of the Query Reader: Reflections on Web Search* (pp. 49–58). Amsterdam: Institute of Network Culture. https://networkcultures.org/query/wp-content/uploads/sites/4/2014/06/4.Dirk_Lewandowski.pdf

Lewandowski, D. (2019). The web is missing an essential part of infrastructure: An Open Web index. *Communications of the ACM*, 62(4), 24–24.

Lovink, G. & Tkacz, N. (2015). MoneyLab: Sprouting New Digital-Economic Forms. In: *Moneylab: An Intervention in Digital Economy*. Amsterdam: Institute of Networked Culture.

Mager, A., Norocel, O. C., & Rogers, R. (2023). Advancing search engine studies: The evolution of Google critique and intervention. *Big Data & Society*, 10(2). (Original work published 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517231191528>

Noble, S. U. (2018). *Algorithms of Oppression, How Search Engines Reinforce Racism*. New York: New York University Press

Nussbaumer, A., Pope, A., & Neville, K. (2023). A framework for applying ethics-by-design to decision support systems for emergency management. *Information Systems Journal*, 33(1), 34–55. <https://doi.org/10.1111/isj.12350>

Ridgway, R. (2021). *Re:search: The Personalised Subject vs. the Anonymous User*. Copenhagen Business School [Phd]. PhD Series No. 21.2021

Ridgway, R. (2023). *Deleterious consequences: How Google's original sociotechnical affordances ultimately shaped 'trusted users' in surveillance capitalism*. *Big Data & Society*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517231171058>

Zuboff, S (2015) Big Other: Surveillance Capitalism and the Prospects of an Information Civilization. *Journal of Information Technology*, 30:75-89.

Zuboff, S. (2019) *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism: The Fight for a Human Future at the New Frontier of Power*. New York: Public Affairs.